

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Davidson**FIRST NAME:** Tamu**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** RP1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Mac OS

Six key concepts in this response paper

1. Steps for writing a good essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper (EUCLID 2024, 12-14)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 16-23)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024,34-39)
5. Why a writer needs a particular style guide (EUCLID 2024, 41-42)
6. Chicago style (EUCLID 2024, 44-57)

A GUIDE FOR GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This period's topic could initially seem uninteresting or unimportant. However, I was excited to participate in the first course, ACA-401D, and have the chance to enhance my writing abilities generally, which I think would help me in my day-to-day work. I reviewed the ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1), including accompanying videos.

Even though English is my native language, I still picked up a lot of new knowledge. Furthermore, the material made it easier for me to review and reinforce the concepts I studied in high and preparatory school.

Learning when and how to use semicolons was new for me, as I had not used them in my writing. A semicolon, for instance, can be used to join two related sentences that do not logically depend on one another and can each stand alone as a grammatically complete phrase or in place of commas (EUCLID 2024, 18). It also dawned on me that, despite my best efforts to write only in United Kingdom (UK) English, I was blending United States (US) and UK English. I discovered a new method to minimize these problems when writing

using Microsoft Word, which was setting the default language to the UK after viewing the video by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck.

In this response paper for Period 1, I will review six concepts: steps for writing a good essay, rules of thumb for writing a paper, punctuation, plagiarism, and why a writer needs a particular style guide and Chicago style.

2) STEPS FOR WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

There are different types of essays, and writing a good academic essay is the focus of the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degree. So, what is an academic essay? ‘An academic essay is non-fictional writing produced as part of academic work’ which seeks ‘to provide the answer(s) to hypothesis aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence’(EUCLID 2024, 7).

The steps for producing a good essay are not linear. However, it is crucial to get started early, identify and answer the key questions to be addressed by the essay and draft an initial plan (EUCLID 2024, 7). I have discovered that starting early is essential for effectively completing an excellent essay, and on occasion, I miscalculated how long it would take to write an essay. This is a habit I would like to improve as I approach essay writing.

These basic steps were noted that should be followed in writing a good academic essay: analyse the question and define key terms, establish the points of view, research the topic by using credible academic sources, take notes from your preliminarily reading, develop your essay plan and organise your ideas, draft your essay into three main parts (introduction, body and conclusion), set the draft aside for one to two days, then review it and make changes, edit and redraft the essay, have a college or friend read it, complete or check your references (important to prevent plagiarism), and finally hand in the essay (EUCLID 2024, 8-12).

I apply these basic steps, to my essay writing process to variable degrees, but not in a linear fashion. For example, I often begin by selecting the topic and focus of the essay, then proceed to research the topic and take notes, then develop a plan and draft the essay, and may conduct additional research if required. Nevertheless, I have identified certain weaknesses, such as analysing the question, defining key terms, establishing viewpoints, devising a plan, and organizing ideas cohesively.

Additionally, I learned that I should use the first person singular when writing an academic paper, which for me has been somewhat daunting, and I am still acclimatising (EUCLID 2024,14). Employing these steps, as noted in Chapter 1, will help me maintain a structured approach, which is essential for producing high-quality essays.

The ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1) provided excellent guidance on the basic steps and key considerations that should be addressed for each step when writing an essay. Most importantly, the steps are non-linear, and beginning writing the essay at an

early stage is essential (EUCLID 2024, 7,11). The rest of the chapters in the ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1), provide guidance on the essential rules to ensure the essay is grammatically correct and follows a standard format, some of which I will be discussing in this paper.

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A GOOD PAPER

The rules of thumb for writing a paper are critical to helping me focus and complete the Ph.D. degree successfully, with the writing of essays being an essential component of a response paper required for most periods. The rules noted are to state the main thesis of your paper at or near the beginning, stay focused, do not lead with, conclude with, or otherwise include such sweeping generalities, write clearly, do not make the writing boring and clumsy, support assertions, take the views you were discussing seriously, do not plagiarize (EUCLID 2024, 12-14).

In this section, not plagiarising is emphasised again, when it may occur, the consequences that could ensue, such as lower grades and a failing grade for the course, and that it is unethical (EUCLID 2024, 14). I noted that implementing these rules of thumb will require that I spend some time editing my own writing.

4) PUNCTUATION

Punctuation marks are essential aspects of good writing, helping to communicate a writer's intended meaning and tone. The ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1) offers extensive guidelines for using punctuation marks properly. It is important to understand and differentiate between correct and incorrect punctuation. I learned that when writing a sentence, as a general rule, 'as little punctuation as necessary should be used while retaining the meaning of the sentence' (EUCLID 2024, 16).

The use of punctuation is an area of writing that I would like to improve. I noted in the reading the proper use of bullet points and full stops and when to punctuate or not, of a colon to show a subclause that follows logically from the text before it, and of semicolons to link two related parts of a sentence that could stand alone as grammatically complete sentences (EUCLID 2024, 18). I also learned how to use semicolons instead of commas in a complex list or sentence to improve clarity, mainly if the list items already include commas (EUCLID 2024, 18).

Additionally, I relearned how to use apostrophes, brackets round, square, angle, and curly, including with other punctuations, dashes and hyphens, ellipses, exclamation, questions, and quotation marks properly. I also learned that American English has different rules about the use of quotation marks (EUCLID 2024, 20 -23).

I found it very useful in this chapter, where concrete examples were shared that can be referred to ensure I am on the right track in using punctuation. This will be extremely helpful as I progress through the PhD degree.

The video reviewed by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck also provided further practical insights on how to improve punctuation using Microsoft Word.

5) PLAGIARISM

Preventing plagiarism is a recurrent theme throughout the documents provided by EULCID, and the ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1) is no different. According to the EULCID ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1), ‘plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information,’ for example, ‘taking someone else’s words or ideas and not giving credit to them’ (EUCLID 2024, 14).

I already knew that plagiarism is unethical and that it is wrong to commit plagiarism. It is a serious offense, and there are potential consequences, such as expulsion, fines, imprisonment, and other penalties that can be meted out if an individual is found to have committed this offense (EUCLID 2024, 34). It also impacts an individual’s integrity and reputation. Therefore, credit to the original author is always required when using a quote, paraphrase, statistic, data, or image from another source.

I noted that plagiarism can be prevented by proper citation of the source or author where required. I got an overview of various citation styles, such as Turabian, Modern Language Association (MLA), and American Psychological Association (APA), and learned the standard steps to create an effective citation list and bibliography. I also learned how to use proper quotation, paraphrasing, and summarizing techniques to use credible sources effectively while avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 35-37).

At Euclid University, students pursuing a global health degree, like me, can use Turabian or WHO rules of style for proper citation. Both styles are new for me as I have mostly used the Oxford Standard Citation of Legal Authorities (OSCOLA) and Harvard referencing, the American Medical Association /American Public Health Association (AMA/APHA), and the APA rules of style.

Students like me can easily find themselves down a rabbit hole with respect to inadvertently committing plagiarism, and I have always taken care to prevent this from occurring. This chapter helped me to feel more confident. I learned that there are instances when you do not have to cite, and this is not plagiarism, such as ‘when the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas. The basic rule is that if it is repeated in many different sources, you can assume it is common knowledge’ (EUCLID 2024, 37).

Additionally, I learned that there is an allowable percentage of plagiarism or an acceptable threshold, but that will depend on whether the author’s text is used with good reason. All papers should be checked for plagiarism with Grammarly premium and percentage submitted (EUCLID Student Orientation 2024, 3-4).

Learning how to avoid and prevent plagiarism is an essential skill that I must hone and adhere to, not only to ensure I avoid the consequences of plagiarism but also to uphold a high standard of ethical professional practice.

6) WHY A WRITER NEEDS A PARTICULAR STYLE GUIDE

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, a style guide is a book or set of documents that gives a set of rules for writing and presenting text that is going to be published (Cambridge Dictionary 2024). Style guides cover various aspects such as sentence lengths, layout, font usage, spelling preferences, voice, structure, and more, tailored to the needs of each publication or company (EUCLID 2024, 41). It is important for academic writing, and there are several existing guides.

I learned it is important to use a standard style or format for writing that can be followed and provides a writer with consistency in their approach. It ensures that the final document reflects the style associated with the organisation rather than the individual writer's personal style. Each organization and individual has its own style. However, within an organisation, it is important that everyone follows a standard to ensure consistency and coherence for all the documents produced (EUCLID 2024, 41). Likewise, at EUCLID, the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and WHO rules are recommended for global health students (EUCLID Student Orientation 2024, 2). EUCLID also recommends American English, but either US or UK English can be used except for in the same document, where only one style should be used (EUCLID 2024, 41). I have opted for UK English as it is used in Jamaica, and I am most comfortable using it. One can imagine that if students used any style they wanted, it would become a major challenge for the teacher.

EUCLID also provides a template for writing papers that includes clear instructions on the style to use, which is very helpful. The video, by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck, provides step-by-step instructions on how to make the necessary edits to the templates for use. Most importantly, I learned that utilising a style guide can streamline proofreading and corrections, saving time. After reviewing Chapter 5, I have a better appreciation for the need to adopt a particular style.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL STYLE

The Chicago Style is the recommended style of EUCLID. The Chicago Style rules encompass guidelines for formatting books and research papers as outlined in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers. It is also often referred to as the 'Turabian style' when used for research papers (EUCLID 2024, 44). It includes specifications for page formatting, abbreviations, acronyms, numbers, dates, quotations, and tables to ensure consistency and clarity in academic writing. The rules cover aspects like capitalization, footnotes, headings, and bibliography formats, providing a comprehensive framework for writers to follow in their academic work.

I learned that there is a CMS Crib Sheet that is a quick reference guide for students who need to learn the requirements of the manual EUCLID 2024, 44). The sheet covered the basics of the Chicago style, including the use of citations, reference lists, and formatting guidelines for papers, which will be very helpful in helping me master this style (EUCLID 2024, 44). This is the first time I am learning about the CMS, and the content of chapter 6 is all new for me.

I learned mainly that in-text citations rather than footnotes are used for spelling Webster's Third New International Dictionary and its chief abridgment (EUCLID 2024, 44). As I progress through the courses, I expect to master this style; whilst it is new, some of the approaches are cross-cutting, and I like other styles I have been exposed to, such as the APA.

8) CONCLUSION

I learned that writing a good academic essay will take a significant investment in time and dedication to relearn and learn the key elements and ingredients. Additionally, before beginning to write the essay, it is essential to choose only one standard of language, UK or USA, as well as a referencing style in keeping with EUCLID's standards. However, if the basic steps for writing an essay are adhered to, along with following EUCLID's prescribed style (CMS) and recommendations, I am well on my way to success. Most importantly, the key to success will be practice, and more practice was cleverly built into the EUCLID training by preparing response papers along with the required feedback from the instructors. This journey through this course will not only improve my academic writing skills but also my current work.

REFERENCES

Cambridge Dictionary. 2024. "Style Guide" Accessed April 20, 2024.
https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/style-guide#google_vignette

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

EUCLID 2024. *EUCLID Student Orientation*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.